

NORMATIVE LEGAL ACTS REGULATING THE ACTIVITIES OF CIVIL SOCIETY INSTITUTIONS

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Abstract: This article analyzes the important role of civil society in the formation and development of democratic politics and the legal system. It defines the further development of civil society institutions, their independent functioning, protection of citizens' rights, freedoms, and interests, raising legal awareness and culture, and the formation of a group of representatives from the Parliamentary Commission and civil society institutions.

Keywords: Civil society institutions, public audit, civic observation, public monitoring, public opinion research.

The Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan serves as the legal foundation for building a new life and a new society in our country. The enshrinement of basic principles for public organizations' activities in the Constitution has created favorable conditions for developing a wide network of such organizations that reflect the interests of all segments of the population.

As noted in the Decree of President Shavkat Mirziyoyev dated June 20, 2017, No. F-4969 "On Measures for the Preparation and Conduct of the Celebration of the 25th Anniversary of the Adoption of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan" [1], based on the provisions and principles enshrined in our Basic Law, an effective national legislative system, state power and administration bodies, and civil society institutions are being formed. Large-scale reforms are being implemented in all spheres and sectors of our life, the socio-economic, political, and military potential of the state is increasing, and the consciousness and thinking of our people are continuously growing.

In our opinion, ample opportunities have been created for public associations to involve citizens in managing state and public affairs and contribute to the exercise of state power with their participation. In particular, to further develop non-governmental non-profit organizations as civil society institutions in our country, ensure their independent activity, protect citizens' rights, freedoms, and interests, and increase their legal awareness and culture, laws of the Republic of Uzbekistan such as "On Guarantees of the Activities of Non-Governmental Non-Profit Organizations" [2], "On Public Funds" [3], "On Citizens' Self-Government Bodies," "On Public Control in the Republic of Uzbekistan" [4], and other legal foundations have been established. As a result, public organizations have begun to embody the characteristics of civil society institutions.

The Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated August 26, 2024 No. PF-124 "On Measures for Further Improvement of the System of State Support for Civil Society Institutions" is a logical continuation of the aforementioned reforms. It aims to create a system of state support for civil society institutions based on the principles of transparency and healthy competition, as well as to establish additional conditions for increasing the effectiveness of socially beneficial programs.

The Decree defines six most important areas of state support for the sphere, which serve to enhance the role of civil society institutions at the current stage of the development of New Uzbekistan:

the first direction, further increasing the activity of civil society institutions in the life of the state and society, as well as the full use of their potential in the development of the socio-economic, political-legal, cultural-spiritual, and humanitarian spheres;

the second direction, promoting the implementation of initiatives aimed at solving pressing problems remaining on the ground, in the interests of society and the real needs of the population;

the third direction - further development of mutually beneficial social partnership between government bodies and civil society institutions;

fourth direction, stimulating the implementation of effective public control by civil society institutions to promote the development of all spheres of state and public life;

the fifth direction is the establishment of ties between civil society institutions and compatriots abroad, as well as strengthening their cooperation with associations abroad;

the sixth direction is defined as strengthening the material and technical base of civil society institutions and creating favorable organizational and legal conditions for them to carry out their activities.

The Decree establishes the following incentives and benefits for civil society institutions:

Firstly, the Public Fund for Support of Civil Society Institutions and its territorial subdivisions are being created under the Parliament.

Now, representatives of the Senate and the Legislative Chamber will alternately chair the Parliamentary Commission for the Management of the Fund. This increases the efficiency of fund management.

Secondly, the activities of "Advisory Groups consisting of representatives of civil society institutions" will be established under the Jokargy Kenes of the Republic of Karakalpakstan and local Kengashes.

Thirdly, state bodies have been granted the right to finance, without tenders, initiated social partnership projects of civil society institutions up to one thousand times the basic calculated value.

Fourthly, in order to expand the participation of citizens in state and public administration, a procedure will be introduced for chairing Public Councils under state bodies by a representative of the civil society institution.

Fifthly, taking into account the social significance of state grants and social order projects, the income tax and social tax rates within the framework of such projects have been reduced by 50 percent for a period of three years. The saved funds will be directed towards the project's goals and will serve to increase its effectiveness.

Sixthly, in order to further simplify the creation of organizations for the disabled, veterans, women, and children, starting from January 1, 2025, the state fee for the registration of such organizations has been reduced by half.

Seventhly, "Civil Society Week" will be held annually in the first week of December. Within its framework, representatives of the sphere will be awarded the badge "For Contribution to the Development of Civil Society" by the Parliamentary Commission.

Eighthly, the National Award "Civil Initiative," awarded every two years by the Parliamentary Foundation, will be established.

A nomination for covering the activities of civil society institutions will be organized at the annual international competition for the "Golden Pen" national award, which is traditionally held among journalists.

The Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated January 9, 2019 No. UP-5618 "On the Fundamental Improvement of the System of Raising Legal Awareness and Legal Culture in Society" was adopted, in which it was stated that work on raising legal culture, primarily in the field of legal education and upbringing, is not carried out systematically and organically, for many years this issue has been considered as the work of law enforcement agencies and some state bodies, and the participation of the family, mahalla and other civil society institutions has not been sufficiently ensured. Based on this, the Decree defines the priority task of cooperation between internal affairs bodies and civil society institutions as "strengthening the interaction of state authorities and administration, including law enforcement agencies and civil society institutions, in carrying out targeted legal advocacy, increasing the role of the media in providing legal information, widespread use of innovative methods of legal advocacy, including expanding the use of web technologies";

On May 4, 2018, the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. UP-5430 "On Measures to Radically Enhance the Role of Civil Society Institutions in the Process of Democratic Renewal of the Country" was adopted. This decree, in essence, became a solid legal basis for a qualitatively new stage of cooperation between the state and civil society institutions. Because it defines the most important directions of state support for civil society institutions, further strengthening their activities, and highlights some unused opportunities and problems in this area.

The decree also defines the task of "adopting a resolution on the approval of the Regulation on the interaction of justice bodies with other state administration bodies, local government bodies, and law enforcement agencies to identify non-governmental non-profit organizations that violate legislation and engage in prohibited activities."

This Decree is an important factor in raising the activities of civil society institutions and non-governmental non-profit organizations (NGOs) to a qualitatively new level. Our compatriots are taking an even more active part in the life of the state and society, making a practical contribution to the accelerated implementation of socio-economic reforms. In accordance with this decree, the practice of organizing hearings of heads of local government bodies on issues of developing the activities of non-governmental non-commercial organizations on the ground, ensuring the protection of their rights and legitimate interests has been introduced;

- Today, an Advisory Council for the Development of Civil Society has been established under the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, which, along with discussing pressing issues of concern to the general public, regularly informing the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan about them, preparing proposals for the introduction of modern mechanisms for effective interaction of state bodies with civil society institutions, measures to support and stimulate their activities, conducting research in this area, introducing new mechanisms based on the study of public opinion and foreign experience, submits proposals to the President on further strengthening cooperation between state and non-state organizations;

- The Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan proclaims the establishment of a democratic state governed by the rule of law in our country. The activities of law enforcement agencies, the prosecutor's office, justice, internal affairs, and other similar bodies play a

leading role in building a democratic state governed by the rule of law, implementing and strengthening legality and legal order. Legality fully operates in a state governed by the rule of law. Without the full implementation of legality, it is impossible to build a civil society. Law enforcement agencies encourage citizens to comply with legality and obey the law. Legality shows what rights a person and citizens have, what the state should do to implement these rights;

- Mass media plays an invaluable role in ensuring the openness and transparency of the activities of internal affairs bodies, as well as in ensuring their interaction with civil society institutions. However, so far, the capabilities of the media are not being used sufficiently, and the initiative, courage, and activity of the media in this regard are not satisfactory. In this area, the introduction of the principles of close cooperation of both sides with the media, the development, creation, and application of effective mechanisms, methods, and forms of interaction are of particular relevance.

In addition, the study of the mechanism and specific forms of constitutional and legal regulation of the interaction and cooperation of internal affairs bodies and civil society institutions, the identification of ways to improve the legal mechanisms of civil society institutions and internal affairs bodies, its procedural and organizational aspects, and the search for ways to improve the cooperation of the parties to these relations are relevant.

The concept of a state governed by the rule of law is closely related to the concept of a democratic state. World experience shows that a democratic, legal state is built not by force and revolution, but by a natural-historical evolutionary path. Of course, in any society, the concept of a state governed by the rule of law is not determined by the existence of certain laws. After all, laws exist as a right in every state, and any authority uses them. The question is what these laws are and how they are implemented.

As noted above, Article 2 of the Law "On Internal Affairs Bodies," which is an important legal basis for the activities of internal affairs bodies, sets out the main tasks of internal affairs bodies, which define that the main tasks of internal affairs bodies are the protection of the rights, freedoms, and legitimate interests of citizens, the property of individuals and legal entities, the constitutional order, ensuring the rule of law, the security of the individual, society, and the state, as well as the prevention of offenses[6].

Over the past period, large-scale work has been carried out to improve the system of internal affairs bodies. In particular, significant work has been done on the development and strengthening of the lower level of internal affairs bodies, organized to maintain public order in mahallas, ensure the safety of citizens, prevent offenses, and combat crime"[7].

The activities of public structures created for the protection of public order and ensuring the safety of citizens on the ground, the upbringing of a healthy generation, ensuring the peaceful and harmonious life of citizens in the family and mahalla, the peaceful resolution of family disputes, the widespread promotion of a healthy lifestyle based on national values, assistance in the fight against crime and the prevention of offenses, as well as cooperation with them, are also of great importance for the internal affairs bodies and other relevant state authorities.

References:

1. See: Collection of Legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan, 2017, No. 25, Art. 536, No. 37, Art. 982.
2. See: Collection of Legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan, 2007, No. 1-2, Art. 2; 2008, No. 51, Art. 500; 2017, No. 37, Art. 978; National Database of Legislation, July 22, 2020, No. 03/20/629/1087; National Database of Legislation, April 21, 2021, No. 03/21/683/0375.
3. See: Bulletin of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan, 2003, No. 9-10, Art. 141; Collection of Legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan, 2007, No. 50-51, Art. 500; 2008, No 52, Art. 513; 2012, No. 15, Art. 164; 2016, No. 17, Art. 173; National Database of Legislation, 04.12.2019, No. 03/19/586/4106; National Database of Legislation, April 21, 2021, No. 03/21/683/0375.
4. See: Collection of Legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan, 2013, No. 17, Art. 219; 2016, No. 17, Art. 173, No. 52, Art. 597; 2017, No. 37, Art. 978; National Database of Legislation, July 24, 2018, No. 03/18/486/1559, October 16, 2018, No. 03/18/498/2051, December 21, 2018, No. 03/18/506/2356; 05.09.2019, No. 03/19/563/3685, 11.09.2019, No. 03/19/566/3734; National Database of Legislation, April 21, 2021, No. 03/21/683/0375, December 10, 2021, No. 03/21/736/1144.
National Database of Legislation, January 10, 2019, No. 06/19/5618/2452, December 11, 2019, No. 06/19/5892/4134; 09.10.2020, No. 07/20/4857/1357; March 17, 2021, No. 06/21/6188/0216, National Database of Legislation, November 30, 2021, No. 06/21/26/1111
6. See: Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated September 16, 2016 No. 3PY-407 "On Internal Affairs Bodies" / Collection of Legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan. No. 38 (746) of September 26, 2016.
7. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated April 10, 2017 No. UP-5005 "On Measures to Radically Increase the Effectiveness of the Activities of Internal Affairs Bodies, Strengthen Their Responsibility for Ensuring Public Order, Reliable Protection of the Rights, Freedoms, and Legitimate Interests of Citizens" // Collection of Legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan. -2017. - P. 243.

